

Performance of phenylthiourea as corrosion inhibitor for aluminum in trichloroacetic acid

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Abstract : The corrosion of aluminum in trichloroacetic acid (TCA) containing phenylthiourea has been studied. In plain TCA, the corrosion rate increases with the acid concentration. At constant acid concentration, the inhibition efficiency (I.E.) of phenylthiourea increases with the inhibitor concentration. At constant inhibitor concentration, the I.E. decreases with the increase of acid concentration. As temperature increases, percentage of inhibition decreases. Plot of $\log (\theta/1 - \theta)$ versus $\log C$ results in a straight line, suggesting that the inhibitors cover both the anodic and cathodic regions through general adsorption following Langmuir isotherm. The curves show very little anodic but significant cathodic polarization.

Keywords : Corrosion, aluminum, trichloroacetic acid, phenylthiourea.

Introduction

Aluminum is known to exhibit passive behaviour in aqueous solutions. Study of the inhibitory action of thiourea, allylthiourea and phenylthiourea for aluminum-copper alloy (4% Cu) in trichloroacetic acid (TCA) has been investigated earlier and in continuation of our earlier study on the effect of TCA on aluminum containing methylthymol blue as inhibitor. We present here our present study on the inhibitive action of phenylthiourea on the corrosion of aluminum in TCA solutions using gravimetric as well as polarization method¹.

Experimental

Rectangular specimens of size $5.0 \times 2.0 \times 0.18$ cm having an area of 0.2414 sq. dm of 2S grade aluminum with small hole of about 5 mm diameter near the upper edge, were used for the determination of the corrosion rate. The specimens were polished according the method described earlier². The specimens were degreased by immersion in A.R. grade acetone and dried in warm air using air dryer and preserved in desiccator till use. The test specimens were immersed in 0.01, 0.05 and 0.10 M TCA solution with and without inhibitors. Phenylthiourea was used as inhibitor in 5, 10, 15 and 20 mM concentration. One specimen only was suspended by a

glass hook, in each beaker containing 230 ml of the test solution and was open to the air at room temperature for 24 h. After the tests, the specimens were cleaned with chromic-phosphate mixture solution. Triplicate experiments were performed in each case and the mean value of the weight loss data were presented in mg/sq. dm. The effect of temperature on corrosion rate was studied at 313, 323 and 333 K for a period of 2 h. Inhibition efficiency energy of activation (E_a), heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) and free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0), were calculated and shown in Table 1. Aluminum specimen having an area of 0.0675 dm² was immersed in 0.01 M TCA with and without 5 mM inhibitor concentration and the potential were recorded against the saturated calomel electrode every 2 min till a constant potential was attained. For polarization study, metal specimens of rectangular design having an area of 0.02585 dm² were exposed to corrosive solutions. Aluminum metal was used as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl was used as reference electrode and auxiliary platinum electrode was placed in a 100 ml corrosive media through which external current was supplied automatically from computerized polarization instrument. The change in potential was measured by potentiostat/galvanostat (Autolab Model-273). Galvanostatic polarization has been taken with and without inhibitors in 0.01 M trichloroacetic acid.

Table 1. Effect of temperature on corrosion loss (CL), inhibitive efficiency (%), energy of activation (E_a), heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) and free energy of adsorption for aluminum in 0.05 M TCA containing phenylthiourea

Immersion period : 2 h, effective specimen area : 0.2414 dm²

System	Temp. (K)						Mean E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	E_a from Arrhenius plot (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Q_{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)		Mean value (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	313		323		333				313-	323-	(ΔG_{ads}^0)	(ΔH_{ads}^0)	(ΔS_{ads}^0)
	CL (mg/dm ²)	I.E. (%)	CL (mg/dm ²)	I.E. (%)	CL (mg/dm ²)	I.E. (%)			313 K	333 K			
A	194.70	-	310.68	-	426.68	-	33.83	32.61	-	-	-	-	-
B	31.89	83.62	86.99	72.00	151.77	64.43	106.58	103.90	-146.40	-31.35	-28.71	47.09	0.2310
C	29.56	84.82	85.87	72.36	141.36	66.87	112.30	109.74	-163.52	-23.25	-27.16	41.90	0.2093
D	25.36	86.97	85.56	72.46	142.55	66.59	135.32	132.44	-210.05	-24.84	-26.55	42.97	0.2093
E	23.61	87.87	74.57	76.00	129.16	69.73	146.09	142.99	-224.88	-28.46	-26.39	46.43	0.2192

A = TCA, B = TCA + 5 mM phenylthiourea, C = TCA + 10 mM phenylthiourea, D = TCA + 15 mM phenylthiourea, E = TCA + 20 mM phenylthiourea.

Inhibition efficiency (I.E.) in percentage has been calculated as follows :

$$I.E. = [(W_u - W_i)/W_u] \times 100$$

where W_u is the weight loss of the metal in uninhibited acid and W_i is the weight loss of a metal in inhibited acid. E_a has been calculated from the slopes of $\log p$ versus $1/T$ (p = corrosion rate, T = absolute temperature) and also with the help of Arrhenius equation.

$$\log p_2/p_1 = E_a/2.303 R [(1/T_1) - (1/T_2)]$$

where p_1 and p_2 are the corrosion rate at temperature T_1 and T_2 respectively. The values of heat of adsorption (Q_{ads}) were calculated by the following equation³.

$$Q_{ads} = 2.303 R [\log (\theta_2/1 - \theta_2) - \log (\theta_1/1 - \theta_1)] \times [T_1 \cdot T_2 / T_2 - T_1]$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 [$\theta = (W_u - W_i)/W_i$] are the fraction of the metal surface covered by the inhibitors at temperature T_1 and T_2 , respectively. The values ΔG_{ads}^0 were calculated from slope of the plot of the following equation⁴.

$$\log C = \log (\theta/1 - \theta) - \log B$$

where $\log B = -1.74 - (\Delta G_{ads}^0/12.303 RT)$ and C is the inhibitor concentration.

The ΔH_{ads}^0 and ΔS_{ads}^0 were calculated using the following equations.

$$\Delta H_{ads}^0 = E_a - RT$$

$$T\Delta S_{ads}^0 = \Delta H_{ads}^0 - \Delta G_{ads}^0$$

Results and discussion

The results are presented in Tables 1-3 and Fig. 1. The pH of 0.01 M TCA was 2.02 while that of the inhibited acid (0.01 M TCA + 1 mM inhibitors) was 1.97 (phenylthiourea). The effect of acid concentration on the inhibitive efficiency of the phenylthiourea is shown in Table 2. The I.E. decreases with the increase in acid concentration. At constant acid concentration, the I.E. of the phenylthiourea increases with the inhibitor concentration, e.g. in 0.01 M TCA the I.E. was found to be 91.18,

Table 2. Effect of acid concentration on corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm) and inhibition efficiency (%) of aluminum in TCA containing phenylthiourea

Effective area of specimen : 0.2414 sq. dm; immersion period : 24 h, Temp. : 301 ± 1 K

Inhibitor	Inhibitor concentration (mM)	Acid concentration					
		0.01 M		0.05 M		0.10 M	
		Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	I.E. (%)	Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	I.E. (%)	Corrosion loss (mg/sq. dm)	I.E. (%)
Blank	-	118.88	-	1189.3	-	2452.09	-
Phenylthiourea	5	10.49	91.18	107.28	90.08	1068.87	56.41
	10	11.60	90.24	80.40	93.29	937.19	61.78
	15	10.77	90.94	96.45	91.89	730.23	70.22
	20	8.28	93.04	73.74	93.80	252.81	89.69

Note

Table 3. Polarisation data and inhibition efficiency of phenylthiourea for aluminum in 0.01 M TCA

Surface area of specimen : 0.02585 sq. dm, inhibitor concentration : 5 mM

System	E_{corr} (mV)	Corrosion current density from intersection of anodic and cathodic Tafel lines I_{corr} (A/cm ²)	Tafel slope (mV/decade)			Inhibitor efficiency (%)	
			Cathodic ($-\beta_c$)	Anodic ($+\beta_a$)	B (mV)	Polarisation (%)	Weight loss (%)
Blank	-755	0.082	963	231	97	-	-
Phenylthiourea	-755	0.012	845	222	92	85.36	91.98

β_a = anodic Tafel constant, β_c = cathodic Tafel constant.

90.24, 90.94 and 93.04% with respect to 5, 10, 15 and 20 mM inhibitor concentration respectively (Table 2).

The effect of temperature on the corrosion of aluminum is shown in Table 1. It shows that the increase in corrosion rate may be due to thermal activated kinetics⁵. The I.E. for phenylthiourea was decreased (87.87, 76.00 and 69.73% at 313, 323 and 333 K respectively at 4 mM inhibitor concentration) with raising the temperature. Mean E_a values were calculated for aluminum in 0.05 M TCA is 33.83 kJ mol⁻¹ while in acid containing inhibitors, the mean E_a values are found to be higher than that of uninhibited system (Table 1). The higher values of mean E_a indicate physical adsorption of the inhibitors on the metal surface⁶, which leads to an increase in the energy barrier for the corrosion process. The values of E_a calculated from the slope of Arrhenius plot.

From Table 1 it is evident that in all cases the values of Q_{ads} are negative (-224.88 to -23.25 kJ mol⁻¹). The negative values show that the adsorption, and hence the inhibition efficiency, decreases with a rise in temperature⁷. The mean ΔG_a^0 values are negative almost in all cases and lie in the range of -28.71 to -26.39 kJ mol⁻¹

(phenylthiourea). The negative mean value of ΔG_{ads}^0 suggest that the inhibitor molecules are strongly adsorbed on the metal surface; the values also indicate a spontaneous adsorption of the inhibitor molecules and usually characterize their strong interactions with the metal surface. It is found that the ΔG_a^0 values are more positive than -40 kJ mol⁻¹ indicating that inhibitors are physically adsorbed on the metal surface⁸.

The enthalpy changes (ΔH_a^0) are positive indicating the endothermic nature of the reaction. Higher temperature favours the corrosion process. The entropy (ΔS_a^0) values are positive confirming that the corrosion process is entropically favourable. A specimen of aluminum when immersed in 0.05 M TCA developed a steady state potential of -714 mV vs SCE. In the presence of phenylthiourea the corrosion potentials was decreased (-662 mV) than the blank.

The polarization behaviour of aluminum in 0.01 M TCA at 5 mM inhibitor concentration under galvanostatic conditions at different current densities in presence and absence of inhibitors is shown in Fig. 1. The values of

Fig. 1. Polarisation curves for corrosion of aluminum in 0.01 M TCA containing 5 mM inhibitor : (*) blank, (■) phenylthiourea.

corrosion current densities in the presence and absence of inhibitor were obtained from the plot while percentage efficiency was calculated using the relation :

$$\text{I.E. (\%)} = [i_{\text{corr}}(U) - i_{\text{corr}}(i)/i_{\text{corr}}(U)] \times 100$$

The curves show both anodic and cathodic polarization. Thus the open circuit potentials and galvanostatic polarization data suggest that the inhibitors function through general adsorption on cathodic as well as anodic sites on the metal surface.

Mechanism :

Generally, aluminum dissolves in acid solutions due to hydrogen evolution type of attack. The reaction taking place at the micro electrodes of the corrosion cell being represented as under,

followed by the reaction

In the case of dissolution of aluminum in TCA the reaction in the initial stages appear to be⁹

Most organic inhibitors are compounds with at least one polar unit, having atoms of nitrogen, oxygen, sulfur and in some cases, selenium and phosphorus. Amine type inhibitors have electron-donating ability and their action is attributed to the adsorption of the inhibitor molecules on the metal surface through an unshared pair of electrons belonging to the nitrogen atom¹⁰. Tests on aniline and alkyl derivatives show that as the side chain is made longer, the efficiency increases. In the present investigation, it appears that the replacement of an amino hydrogen atom by phenyl group improves the inhibitive action. These results are in good agreement with earlier observations¹¹.

High I.E. of these compounds may be attributed to the presence of extensively delocalized electrons on the phenyl rings, planarity and presence of lone pair of electrons on N- and S- atoms, which favors greater adsorption of these compounds on the metal surface.

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